

B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p), gd3 dispersion correction

Top two layers are fully relaxed. The atoms representing 3d and further for the silicon crystal are fixed at positions corresponding to bulk (both silicon and hydrogen (direction) atoms).

Acetophenone molecule

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	8	0	-2.215808	-1.306652	0.000385
2	1	0	0.077709	-2.180431	-0.000285
3	6	0	-1.699040	-0.205107	0.000070
4	6	0	2.589935	0.114535	-0.000028
5	6	0	-0.204938	-0.058495	0.000001
6	6	0	1.966423	-1.135146	-0.000190
7	6	0	0.579756	-1.220675	-0.000150
8	6	0	1.820080	1.276292	0.000186
9	6	0	0.429404	1.190818	0.000167
10	1	0	3.672173	0.181509	-0.000060
11	1	0	2.564269	-2.039511	-0.000337
12	1	0	2.301374	2.247613	0.000327
13	1	0	-0.153972	2.103212	0.000339
14	6	0	-2.554772	1.048294	-0.000348
15	1	0	-3.603499	0.756373	-0.000581
16	1	0	-2.346611	1.660803	0.881819
17	1	0	-2.346071	1.660550	-0.882554

E = -385.012908 Hartrees

2-dimer cluster

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	1	0	1.891478	3.051377	-1.564139
2	1	0	1.943516	3.267952	0.962059
3	1	0	-1.947703	3.059037	-1.485705
4	1	0	-1.895666	3.275596	1.040492
5	1	0	5.057513	1.890068	-0.256872
6	1	0	-5.062322	1.910219	-0.050148
7	1	0	-0.065971	0.028168	-3.081739
8	1	0	0.060261	0.553861	3.050715
9	1	0	3.772271	0.020605	-3.160134
10	1	0	3.898684	0.546220	2.972305
11	1	0	-3.904152	0.035829	-3.003277
12	1	0	-3.777838	0.561525	3.128953
13	1	0	5.043007	-1.462520	-1.691520
14	1	0	5.136782	-1.084552	1.718755
15	1	0	-5.143424	-1.370743	-1.504185
16	1	0	-5.036430	-1.145681	1.918677
17	14	0	1.935010	2.399502	-0.234889
18	14	0	-1.921211	2.392566	-0.158140
19	14	0	0.020670	1.095296	-0.117560
20	14	0	3.832785	1.088909	-0.171203
21	14	0	-3.844925	1.108554	-0.042721
22	14	0	-0.142810	-0.629638	-1.723180
23	14	0	0.141481	-0.300069	1.799790
24	14	0	3.847552	-0.588784	-1.812391
25	14	0	3.877991	-0.285189	1.728654
26	14	0	-3.882898	-0.587900	-1.648980
27	14	0	-3.852399	-0.248132	1.886050
28	14	0	1.881117	-1.424903	-0.844373
29	14	0	2.000653	-1.744835	1.439470
30	14	0	-1.883532	-1.237449	1.079351
31	14	0	-2.007343	-1.976281	-1.108035

E = -4352.435339 Hartrees

Hemihydrate

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	1	0	1.864466	2.095536	-2.730374
2	1	0	1.882675	3.415531	-0.565061
3	1	0	-1.975264	2.078937	-2.687965
4	1	0	-1.957055	3.398932	-0.522653
5	1	0	5.026319	1.686431	-1.022495
6	1	0	-5.094969	1.642677	-0.910708
7	1	0	-0.041181	-1.316520	-2.754186
8	1	0	0.003020	1.887695	2.501990
9	1	0	3.797549	-1.299926	-2.796584
10	1	0	3.841750	1.904290	2.459592
11	1	0	-3.879911	-1.333115	-2.711789
12	1	0	-3.835710	1.871100	2.544387
13	1	0	5.080948	-1.904725	-0.843199
14	1	0	5.127822	-0.102136	2.080574
15	1	0	-5.121593	-1.955815	-0.749333
16	1	0	-5.081819	-0.198140	2.219509
17	14	0	1.898470	2.104844	-1.249680
18	14	0	-1.958114	2.074151	-1.202378
19	14	0	-0.002928	0.960532	-0.575599
20	14	0	3.809161	0.988921	-0.596535
21	14	0	-3.869140	0.946876	-0.539104
22	14	0	-0.042764	-1.285560	-1.245939
23	14	0	0.069629	0.577843	1.766331
24	14	0	3.835388	-1.238224	-1.316939
25	14	0	3.876412	0.620195	1.720284
26	14	0	-3.876162	-1.288854	-1.223533
27	14	0	-3.898146	0.592017	1.791168
28	14	0	1.930023	-2.051427	-0.171392
29	14	0	1.985411	-0.785970	1.898927
30	14	0	-1.917939	-0.635949	1.541342
31	14	0	-1.952493	-2.176032	-0.139613

32 1 0 1.947662 -3.517845 0.085565

E = -4353.067894 Hartrees

Ap-db-allyl

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	1	0	3.030076	3.386184	-1.296137
2	1	0	3.059170	3.392869	1.239690
3	1	0	-0.690734	4.334631	-1.255940
4	1	0	-0.661632	4.341366	1.279885
5	1	0	5.775024	1.384923	-0.054256
6	1	0	-4.032916	3.885057	0.051699
7	1	0	0.437174	1.062050	-3.070168
8	1	0	0.507529	1.078194	3.085027
9	1	0	4.156673	0.113709	-3.110607
10	1	0	4.227371	0.129967	3.045003
11	1	0	-3.282899	2.010185	-3.030129
12	1	0	-3.212167	2.026476	3.125298
13	1	0	4.991278	-1.726297	-1.767624
14	1	0	5.061402	-1.690354	1.686869
15	1	0	-4.875476	0.798473	-1.670097
16	1	0	-4.818158	0.819262	1.784189
17	14	0	2.873380	2.645906	-0.022966
18	14	0	-0.867529	3.584540	0.014274
19	14	0	0.695275	1.849164	-0.029468
20	14	0	4.388894	0.906870	-0.045258
21	14	0	-3.049649	2.809730	0.007321
22	14	0	0.268950	0.389318	-1.770772
23	14	0	0.320684	0.398812	1.774041
24	14	0	3.990792	-0.625077	-1.830548
25	14	0	4.071331	-0.579253	1.759936
26	14	0	-3.474089	1.295341	-1.751191

27	14	0	-3.414967	1.319651	1.828629
28	14	0	1.795218	-1.267995	-1.150965
29	14	0	1.884658	-1.257395	1.229925
30	14	0	-1.843762	-0.361075	1.216455
31	14	0	-1.869090	-0.341274	-1.172617
32	8	0	0.975485	-2.807187	-1.191219
33	6	0	0.213102	-2.893398	-0.012370
34	6	0	1.090018	-3.024062	1.210044
35	1	0	0.541198	-3.269860	2.116860
36	1	0	1.850233	-3.789912	1.038034
37	6	0	-3.947973	-3.065806	-0.066506
38	6	0	-1.116758	-2.634554	-0.018515
39	6	0	-3.334274	-2.845963	1.159214
40	6	0	-1.929273	-2.361758	1.241263
41	6	0	-3.285654	-2.836232	-1.264439
42	6	0	-1.891736	-2.312766	-1.285624
43	1	0	-4.973335	-3.420219	-0.087939
44	1	0	-3.882368	-2.986455	2.083514
45	1	0	-1.441875	-2.713160	2.149184
46	1	0	-3.791636	-2.982054	-2.211598
47	1	0	-1.343862	-2.622016	-2.174547

E = -4736.936036 Hartrees

Ap-db-flagpole

Center Atomic Atomic Coordinates (Angstroms)
Number Number Type X Y Z

1	1	0	-5.047971	0.766801	0.944614
2	1	0	-4.852506	0.580538	-1.576972
3	1	0	-2.847728	3.913340	0.882741
4	1	0	-2.652264	3.727077	-1.638844
5	1	0	-5.715359	-2.620935	-0.132125
6	1	0	0.084341	5.673144	-0.295215
7	1	0	-1.735009	0.834079	3.016799
8	1	0	-1.260531	0.381937	-3.104212
9	1	0	-3.934678	-2.311640	3.078654
10	1	0	-3.460199	-2.763784	-3.042357
11	1	0	0.464659	3.979799	2.954943
12	1	0	0.939138	3.527656	-3.166067
13	1	0	-3.283126	-4.315493	1.905234
14	1	0	-3.023198	-4.570129	-1.504280
15	1	0	2.563759	4.027051	1.757528
16	1	0	2.836740	3.759789	-1.671749
17	14	0	-4.318696	0.230577	-0.234407
18	14	0	-2.113958	3.377805	-0.295681
19	14	0	-2.139812	1.052006	-0.120527
20	14	0	-4.354371	-2.074733	-0.066195
21	14	0	0.043774	4.206573	-0.183724
22	14	0	-1.024853	0.304953	1.810969
23	14	0	-0.767149	0.031395	-1.737969
24	14	0	-3.257661	-2.825997	1.862437
25	14	0	-2.986183	-3.090094	-1.673970
26	14	0	1.173821	3.491694	1.753174
27	14	0	1.448840	3.240269	-1.809534
28	14	0	-1.072866	-2.028385	1.409505
29	14	0	-0.887524	-2.215316	-1.003784
30	14	0	1.232161	1.033737	-1.029316
31	14	0	1.113977	1.171923	1.328077
32	8	0	2.625956	0.026025	-1.002775
33	1	0	3.751667	-1.879386	-1.908611
34	6	0	3.145136	-0.347060	0.214956
35	6	0	2.613844	0.064307	1.397660
36	1	0	3.055537	-0.313685	2.310819
37	1	0	0.012328	-2.776800	2.101736
38	1	0	0.288231	-3.032947	-1.411585
39	6	0	6.455257	-3.041960	-0.209911
40	6	0	4.302686	-1.259493	0.071876
41	6	0	5.530190	-2.890590	-1.241244
42	6	0	4.467071	-2.001989	-1.106501
43	6	0	6.311241	-2.293740	0.959095
44	6	0	5.247033	-1.409762	1.098509
45	1	0	7.286051	-3.730087	-0.317592
46	1	0	5.637244	-3.463808	-2.155358

47	1	0	7.035745	-2.391759	1.759698
48	1	0	5.161736	-0.816934	2.000985

E = -4737.600889 Hartrees

Ap-eb-allyl

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	1	0	1.847599	-4.280540	-0.117056
2	1	0	1.882913	-3.327387	-2.466858
3	1	0	-1.991893	-4.227552	-0.153390
4	1	0	-1.956442	-3.274472	-2.503218
5	1	0	5.017610	-2.672341	-0.785504
6	1	0	-5.103115	-2.532698	-0.881400
7	1	0	-0.070630	-2.263010	2.625543
8	1	0	0.014815	0.050839	-3.078556
9	1	0	3.767655	-2.315851	2.662197
10	1	0	3.853386	-0.002569	-3.041423
11	1	0	-3.909308	-2.209954	2.589406
12	1	0	-3.823218	0.103582	-3.114505
13	1	0	5.018040	-0.340057	2.028583
14	1	0	5.094942	0.921315	-1.185997
15	1	0	-5.105925	-0.216065	1.938589
16	1	0	-5.035505	1.071277	-1.266816
17	14	0	1.890093	-3.096807	-1.006352
18	14	0	-1.966366	-3.031451	-1.034283
19	14	0	-0.011756	-1.869405	-0.501168
20	14	0	3.800133	-1.911895	-0.486438
21	14	0	-3.877539	-1.822704	-0.536039
22	14	0	-0.059571	-1.155637	1.668959
23	14	0	0.009761	0.174273	-1.605699

24	14	0	3.773442	-1.117532	1.772671
25	14	0	3.852234	0.193830	-1.571923
26	14	0	-3.878221	-1.025628	1.694905
27	14	0	-3.811782	0.298818	-1.630307
28	14	0	1.799117	0.245276	1.595307
29	14	0	1.893282	1.120816	-0.612622
30	14	0	-1.839806	1.189996	-0.589325
31	14	0	-1.885080	0.288229	1.623643
32	8	0	1.263593	1.687511	2.429678
33	6	0	0.079184	2.172528	1.867053
34	6	0	-1.184520	1.822632	2.617617
35	1	0	-1.897643	2.649442	2.628631
36	1	0	-0.943353	1.557740	3.646972
37	6	0	0.122647	4.282791	-1.828244
38	6	0	0.085447	2.761660	0.636814
39	6	0	-1.101287	3.921679	-1.287012
40	6	0	-1.218658	3.033630	-0.103883
41	6	0	1.327230	3.873230	-1.278586
42	6	0	1.395567	2.963819	-0.108796
43	1	0	0.137880	4.928188	-2.700712
44	1	0	-2.020901	4.276019	-1.738808
45	1	0	-1.987218	3.415247	0.574370
46	1	0	2.264118	4.194874	-1.719209
47	1	0	2.172599	3.279582	0.593366

E = -4736.940168 Hartrees

Ap-eb-flagpole

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	1	0	-3.112913	2.701021	-2.476063
2	1	0	-4.171535	2.924086	-0.182400
3	1	0	-4.047059	-1.022983	-2.545074
4	1	0	-5.105677	-0.799931	-0.251410
5	1	0	-1.767913	5.570217	-0.732194
6	1	0	-4.230352	-4.246080	-0.914206
7	1	0	-0.300188	0.023835	-2.918101
8	1	0	-2.870053	0.565257	2.648805
9	1	0	0.633623	3.746918	-2.849764
10	1	0	-1.936128	4.288352	2.717949
11	1	0	-1.234029	-3.699105	-2.987589
12	1	0	-3.803934	-3.157766	2.579916
13	1	0	1.779791	4.637917	-0.916749
14	1	0	0.299518	5.007491	2.167293
15	1	0	-0.660848	-5.085992	-1.102504
16	1	0	-2.173579	-4.831227	1.984440
17	14	0	-2.962397	2.638465	-0.998736
18	14	0	-3.894284	-1.089363	-1.066526
19	14	0	-2.269198	0.475006	-0.474755
20	14	0	-1.359431	4.197222	-0.411246
21	14	0	-3.218171	-3.241456	-0.551757
22	14	0	-0.302395	-0.025920	-1.453672
23	14	0	-1.678584	0.275647	1.789904
24	14	0	0.767756	3.639370	-1.363638
25	14	0	-0.764827	4.015368	1.845922
26	14	0	-1.070634	-3.707317	-1.497704
27	14	0	-2.636113	-3.442006	1.705651
28	14	0	1.069282	1.467603	-0.344134
29	14	0	0.109840	1.810675	1.857629
30	14	0	0.270860	-2.009776	-0.401569
31	8	0	2.544135	0.617791	-0.224428
32	1	0	4.739519	1.023758	-1.184598
33	6	0	2.918156	-0.704897	-0.207621
34	6	0	2.139852	-1.823320	-0.287436
35	1	0	2.720633	-2.740137	-0.286467
36	1	0	1.109351	1.542947	2.929083
37	6	0	7.204426	-0.965982	0.042636
38	6	0	4.402182	-0.799596	-0.099829
39	6	0	6.596558	0.100290	-0.618959
40	6	0	5.209197	0.189479	-0.680286
41	6	0	6.411447	-1.941606	0.645374
42	6	0	5.023757	-1.858535	0.576750

43	1	0	8.285215	-1.030793	0.097087
44	1	0	7.204374	0.867297	-1.085866
45	1	0	6.873379	-2.762691	1.182046
46	1	0	4.419032	-2.606447	1.075315
47	14	0	-0.818317	-1.921580	1.775300
48	1	0	0.155827	-2.180398	2.873311

E = -4737.586474 Hartrees

Molecular Adsorption

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	1	0	-5.267461	-0.063476	-0.066536
2	1	0	-4.333681	-0.526482	-2.378458
3	1	0	-3.700028	3.441394	-0.135363
4	1	0	-2.766229	2.978397	-2.447279
5	1	0	-5.023452	-3.625352	-0.645563
6	1	0	-0.891741	5.613300	-0.826958
7	1	0	-2.741854	0.965607	2.732635
8	1	0	-0.475203	-0.158251	-2.879074
9	1	0	-4.308852	-2.538295	2.801628
10	1	0	-2.042221	-3.662196	-2.810325
11	1	0	-1.174888	4.469494	2.664023
12	1	0	1.091788	3.345600	-2.947927

13	1	0	-2.920062	-4.460846	2.239877
14	1	0	-1.768604	-5.103263	-0.922900
15	1	0	1.082630	4.827251	2.000859
16	1	0	2.426248	4.107656	-1.086939
17	14	0	-4.153624	-0.580817	-0.903819
18	14	0	-2.582225	2.925755	-0.971055
19	14	0	-2.267065	0.688878	-0.389799
20	14	0	-3.849096	-2.800671	-0.335533
21	14	0	-0.716359	4.197662	-0.465696
22	14	0	-1.538553	0.610020	1.878604
23	14	0	-0.376062	-0.247212	-1.368705
24	14	0	-3.232710	-3.043760	1.913519
25	14	0	-1.903757	-3.669746	-1.318927
26	14	0	-0.093223	3.928126	1.779909
27	14	0	1.210958	3.332330	-1.466103
28	14	0	-1.357968	-1.689589	1.474866
29	14	0	-0.107511	-2.398137	-0.359877
30	14	0	1.074115	1.284906	-0.277431
31	14	0	0.621333	1.644557	2.090829
32	8	0	2.745171	0.491937	-0.222996
33	1	0	4.093926	-0.085928	1.636097
34	6	0	3.450303	-0.267411	-0.939827
35	6	0	6.663578	-2.227071	1.037822
36	6	0	4.569606	-0.938147	-0.286787
37	6	0	5.811536	-1.375940	1.746658
38	6	0	4.769512	-0.736354	1.094771
39	6	0	6.471501	-2.439277	-0.327917
40	6	0	5.432748	-1.798704	-0.990140
41	1	0	7.476145	-2.728027	1.551618
42	1	0	5.959804	-1.218828	2.808182
43	1	0	7.130540	-3.103823	-0.873314
44	1	0	5.293270	-1.978698	-2.047789
45	6	0	3.112958	-0.456380	-2.383415
46	1	0	2.420188	-1.302727	-2.461523
47	1	0	2.603792	0.427994	-2.766891
48	1	0	3.988593	-0.672505	-2.991998

E = -4737.489469 Hartrees

2+2 adsorption across C=O

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	1	0	2.119087	-4.269322	0.711199
2	1	0	2.132284	-3.844552	-1.788944
3	1	0	-1.718973	-4.385678	0.671174
4	1	0	-1.705782	-3.960939	-1.828978
5	1	0	5.225146	-2.712262	-0.294051
6	1	0	-4.892126	-3.018949	-0.399562
7	1	0	0.099345	-1.789586	2.957752
8	1	0	0.131340	-0.758727	-3.111062
9	1	0	3.936465	-1.673438	2.997692
10	1	0	3.968473	-0.642411	-3.071128
11	1	0	-3.737360	-1.906089	2.917561
12	1	0	-3.705369	-0.874996	-3.151113
13	1	0	5.160050	0.088179	1.920877
14	1	0	5.176606	0.728524	-1.457163
15	1	0	-5.050009	-0.170699	1.840920
16	1	0	-5.024835	0.393554	-1.567919
17	14	0	2.119302	-3.304502	-0.412510
18	14	0	-1.736345	-3.407729	-0.446983
19	14	0	0.164429	-2.077627	-0.180164
20	14	0	3.974903	-1.956910	-0.164185
21	14	0	-3.698540	-2.200999	-0.217777
22	14	0	0.146795	-0.810645	1.814010
23	14	0	0.087424	-0.268406	-1.701534
24	14	0	3.920033	-0.736772	1.832501
25	14	0	3.995147	-0.148045	-1.669475

26	14	0	-3.797224	-0.972780	1.783696
27	14	0	-3.777220	-0.400141	-1.749342
28	14	0	2.004844	0.681747	1.627480
29	14	0	2.000846	0.599868	-0.677975
30	14	0	-1.876707	0.722022	-0.933129
31	14	0	-1.880768	0.310711	1.363213
32	8	0	-2.016603	2.021403	1.396700
33	1	0	-0.367887	3.603130	1.986535
34	6	0	-1.859389	2.493434	0.015707
35	6	0	1.908231	4.608348	-0.329917
36	6	0	-0.537840	3.230600	-0.115046
37	6	0	1.297658	4.443858	0.910148
38	6	0	0.089989	3.755351	1.018735
39	6	0	1.294737	4.085495	-1.468618
40	6	0	0.078172	3.408844	-1.359612
41	1	0	2.855768	5.128334	-0.410872
42	1	0	1.770232	4.835020	1.803825
43	1	0	1.756810	4.205482	-2.442250
44	1	0	-0.388643	3.010615	-2.255044
45	6	0	-3.046317	3.397719	-0.306799
46	1	0	-3.988620	2.852390	-0.215902
47	1	0	-3.063320	4.235861	0.396963
48	1	0	-2.964156	3.796379	-1.321225

E = -4737.522804 Hartrees